

Sociology of Mental Health: Understanding the Relationship Between the Dynamics of Society and Mental Health*

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**Mental Health Spaces in the Context of Space and Sociology of Mental Health is the second part of the master's thesis named Bakırköy Mental Health and Neurological Diseases Training and Research Hospital Example .*

Abstract

This thesis chapter aims to understand the relationship between the dynamics of society and mental health by emphasizing the importance of research on the sociology of mental health. The main purpose of mental health sociology is to explain that the mental and mental health of individuals depends on social and structural factors beyond personal factors. This thesis section primarily presents a review of earlier studies investigating mental health as a social phenomenon and its effects on community mental health. In this context, the effects of social interactions, social norms, institutions and power relations on mental health are examined. Then, different sociological theories and approaches are evaluated to understand the effects of social factors on mental health. social classes, gender, ethnicity, the effects of factors such as age and sexuality on mental health are discussed in detail in this thesis. This thesis also examines inequalities in access to mental health services and the role of social structures in health care. It is discussed how factors such as economic resources, health insurance and social support networks affect the differences in access to mental health services and how this can lead to injustices. Finally, this thesis chapter deals with the feelings and attitudes of the society towards mental health. It examines how the presence of mental health stigma affects individuals' help-seeking behaviors, their application to mental health services, and their adherence to treatment. social norms, the role of media and cultural factors on mental health is also discussed in detail in this section. In addition to emphasizing the importance and contributions of mental health sociology, this thesis also presents policy recommendations that can be made to ensure equal access to mental health services, reduce stigma and create a supportive environment for the mental health of the community. This thesis section presents a sociological perspective in the field of mental health, emphasizing the need for a complex and multifaceted understanding of mental health and encouraging new research to better understand the effects of societal factors on mental health. It also offers policy recommendations to reduce stigma and create a supportive environment for the mental health of the community. This thesis section presents a sociological perspective in the field of mental health, emphasizing the need for a complex and multifaceted understanding of mental health and encouraging new research to better understand the effects of societal factors on mental health. It also offers policy recommendations to reduce stigma and create a supportive environment for the mental health of the community. This thesis section presents a sociological perspective in the field of mental health, emphasizing the need for a complex and multifaceted understanding of mental health

and encouraging new research to better understand the effects of societal factors on mental health.

Entrance

The relationship of sociology with health is examined in the context of medicine, psychiatry, the physician and the patient's social framework. The sociology of health is discussed in the context of the education of doctors and nurses, developments in patient roles, the definition of the disease, institutional health organizations (institutions such as asylums, hospitals). The disease is usually seen as a biological phenomenon in the patient's body. However, according to the definition made by the World Health Organization in 1946, health is not merely the absence of disease or infirmity, but a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being. The concepts of illness and health may differ according to the cultural values and beliefs of societies. Various social attributes such as age, gender, status, culture can affect the feeling of illness and health. While health is generally defined as the ability to perform the basic functions and functions of the body in a biological sense, disease is considered as the deterioration of this condition. The functionalist perspective defines illness as a state of inhibition of the individual's benefit in the social sense. While the concept of health is defined as self-actualization and participation in social life, it has led to criticism of individuals with disabilities. Critical theory argues that health and illness are shaped by capitalist relations of production rather than by the experiences of the individual. It conceptualizes that diseases are caused by social factors such as malnutrition and unhealthy housing, and therefore there is a relationship between capital and health. Poststructuralist theory, on the other hand, states that the body is controlled by the power and the right to speak on the body is given to the power. Defending that control over population and body is a micro-level power strategy, Foucault used the concept of "biopower". Feminist theory emphasizes that definitions of health and disease focus on regulating the female body and limiting sexuality. The feminist perspective argues that women are often criticized and expected to fulfill their usual roles (e.g., mother, wife) when trying to move from their "normal" to the sick role.

Health sociology is examined in three different forms of analysis: "phenomenological approach that prioritizes the experience of illness", "a historical sociological approach that tries to understand the emergence of mental hospitals and clinics responsible for deviations" and "critical sociological approach" (Turner, 2017: 32). The emergence of diseases and health in different forms in different classes shows the economic dimension of health. The critical health sociology approach shows capitalism as the root cause of ill health and disease and proposes a general analysis on the basis of power inequalities of the social system to understand the cause of disease. Critical theory emphasizes that health is affected by social inequalities and that low-income social groups experience limitations in accessing health care. Also, critical theory spatially addresses the problem of housing and states that it is actually a public health problem (Turner, 2017: 14). Socially, the rate of contracting the disease is higher in the "other" neighborhoods of the city, around factories, and in areas where healthy living needs such as clean water, food and shelter are not met.

Sociology tries to understand the meaning of social action as the experience of social individuals. The problem of social order in classical sociology has left its place to the experience of the individual in modern sociology. In this context, the sociology of health and illness has focused on the individual patient and patient experience rather than a social health perspective. Sociology of mental health is considered a special field of sociology of health and

covers many disciplines such as sociology, psychology, economics. Researching and analyzing how mental illness relates to social, political and economic concepts is an important focus. Mental health sociology is concerned with how mentally ill people exist within power relations in society. Psychiatry, it is an institutional form of social control that aims to cut deviations and irregularities within social groups (Foucault, 2019: 199). The sociology of mental health or illness is a critical analysis of the discourse of psychiatry and medical power in a poststructuralist sense. Considering that the concept of mental illness has changed historically and has different meanings periodically, it is argued that mental illness and insanity are social discourses. Foucault (2012) seeks to understand the relationship between certain medical discourses and the use of force in society, and how alliances between discourses, practices and professional groups have developed over time. Considering that the concept of mental illness has changed historically and has different meanings periodically, it is argued that mental illness and insanity are social discourses. Foucault (2012) seeks to understand the relationship between certain medical discourses and the use of force in society, and how alliances between discourses, practices and professional groups have developed over time. Considering that the concept of mental illness has changed historically and has different meanings periodically, it is argued that mental illness and insanity are social discourses. Foucault (2012) seeks to understand the relationship between certain medical discourses and the use of force in society, and how alliances between discourses, practices and professional groups have developed over time.

“We have now come to conclusions, to the point where the sociologist bites the psychiatric hand that fed him with the data. Because psychiatry forces our attention to situation-specific inconveniences, psychiatry has ways of embodying and rationalizing common attitudes about this aspect of behavior rather than taking us beyond these concepts. Therefore, the psychiatrist, who carries a significant workload in the diagnosis and closure phase in a practice or hospital, will generally tend to respond spontaneously to the behavior of the individual with whom he/she is interviewing for diagnostic purposes” (Goffman, 2020: 254).

According to Foucault, the discourse of professional psychiatry developed a new form of power by exercising dominance over bodies. Foucault named the forms of surveillance that developed especially through mental health spaces as panoptism and tried to understand how it developed in this regard. Within the sociology of mental health, Foucault's conceptualization of the discourse of scientific knowledge plays a key role in explaining the domination of mental health professionals. The power struggle shaped around the body and the development of forms of power-domination in connection with mental health spaces supply an important path for the progress of mental health sociology. Diseases should not be thought of as natural events that occur in the world independently of the language they describe.

“I guess psychiatrists hardly suspect that they assume and promote a prearranged harmony and balance that is almost too good to be true. Because for a person who thinks that everything in the world is right, what could be more pleasing than finding scientific evidence that the type of bad behavior that we cannot explain in our own way is only due to the disease of the person who behaves like that, and therefore the worse he behaves, the sicker he is? (Goffman, 2020: 258).

He says that psychiatry discourse alone cannot produce information about socially produced mental and mental illnesses, and that social psychiatry or mental health sociology is

important. At this point, stigmatizing many non-organic functional mental disorders with the stigma of illness means punishment for insanity.

“According to Foucault, we know or see things to the extent our language allows, because we can never grasp or know 'reality' nakedly without language. Scientific discourse, like all forms of knowledge, is simply a collection of metaphors. Scientific knowledge of the world is a form of narrative (it is a story), and the sciences, like all narratives, rely on different linguistic conventions (for example, certain styles of writing). Narrative is a set of events within a language and language is a self-referential system, nothing appears outside of language. Thus, what we know about the "world" is simply the result of arbitrary conventions we have adopted to describe the world. Different societies and historical periods have different conventions and therefore different realities” (Turner, 2017: 17).

By emphasizing that the individual is both a historical subject and an object, Foucault states that the subject is constantly set up in a power relationship and normalized within the institutions of domination. He criticizes that modern power regulates with micro-discipline strategies and controls the normalization of the individual instead of open violence policies. Foucault states that modern architectural spaces function as spaces of normalization rather than just new buildings. It says that spaces such as workhouses, hospitals, prisons, and schools serve control strategies. Foucault emphasizes that interdisciplinary architecture is not just new buildings, but spaces of power to reshape people. In summary, mental health states that the power regulates the individual morally through the discourses of medicine and disease, that these discourses occupy daily life, and as a result, a new human body policy is organized. It focuses on the body and its reproduction through modern forms of power, domination, systems of control, and contemporary human rights knowledge. Mental health spaces are a phenomenon that is tried to be discussed in this thesis.

Basic Concepts of Mental Health Sociology

Theoretical explanations of mental health and illness gained rapid attention towards the middle of the 20th century. Many studies in the literature have shown that disadvantaged socio-economic situations are associated with mental illness (Hudson, 2005; Johnson, Cohen, Dohrenwend, Link, & Brook, 1999; Borge, Rutter, Côté, & Tremblay, 2004). The critical perspective suggests that economic hardships increase the risk of mental illness. The interactionist perspective, on the other hand, examines how cultural concepts appear, are applied, and changed in mental illness studies. Unlike traditional views of mental illness, in the interactionist approach, symptoms are viewed as cultural definitions rather than individual characteristics. Such studies examine how concepts of mental illness appear in certain social conditions, it deals with which groups force definitions of normality and abnormality, how these definitions apply to individuals, and why these concepts change, which social and cultural forces are responsible (Horwitz, 2007). These perspectives were formed by being influenced by a broad sociological perspective such as structuralism, postmodernism, feminism, phenomenology, ethnomethodology. These approaches argue that the factors affecting mental health are specific social positions. It mainly focuses on how disadvantaged situations created by social positions affect mental health. It was formed by being influenced by a broad sociological perspective such as ethnomethodology. These approaches argue that the factors affecting mental health are specific social positions. It mainly focuses on how disadvantaged situations created by social positions affect mental health. It was formed by being influenced by a broad sociological perspective such as ethnomethodology. These approaches argue that

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Discussing conceptualizations on the sociology of mental health, social scientists touched upon issues such as the structure of the mind, the form of the disease, the condition of patients, psychiatry and medical treatment, and studied the social, political, economic and cultural aspects of mental health as well as the biological aspect (Aneshensel & Phelan, 1999). These studies cited disadvantaged social positions and social stress as social causes of mental illness. Social stress theory, a prominent conceptualization in the 1980s, says that mental health problems are linked to social status and life experiences. This approach argues that mental health problems are affected by exposure to social stress (social role and position-related life experiences), as well as vulnerability to stress (low level of social support, self-esteem, or mastery) (Avison, 2005). McLeod and Pescosolido, 2007). The literature on the social determinants of mental health focuses on various social variables such as socio-economic status, gender, age, and race-ethnicity (Avison, McLeod, & Pescosolido, 2007). Mental health sociology also includes many discussions such as the socially disadvantaged social position (stigma) of mental patients and the social stress created by modern life (Goffman, 2018). Research that tried to explain the connection of the socio-economic status of the individual with mental and mental health appeared in the late 1950s. In recent years, studies on the temporal ordering of the relationship between socio-economic status and mental health have been evaluated, and as a result of these studies, the issue of schizophrenia and social class later became controversial and was rejected by some (Aneshensel and Phelan, 2008). 1999). The sociology of mental health, which started to say that mental illnesses are not solely based on genetic factors and damaged nerve cells, drew attention to the social causes of mental health in this sense. For example, the orientation of the gender problem between men and women, which traps women in secluded homes behind the society, is an important risk factor for the occurrence of psychological problems in women (Başterzi, 2017). The feeling of worthlessness, insecurity, and self-sufficiency experienced by women are among the factors affecting mental health. This debate about gender differences in mental illness has recently been reconsidered by national and international data. The sociology of mental health, which started to say that it is not based on damaged nerve cells, drew attention to the social causes of mental health in this sense. For example, the orientation of the gender problem between men and women, which traps women in secluded homes behind the society, is an important risk factor for the occurrence of psychological problems in women (Başterzi, 2017). The feeling of worthlessness, insecurity, and self-sufficiency experienced by women are among the factors affecting mental health. This debate about gender differences in mental illness has recently been reconsidered by national and international data. The sociology of mental health, which started to say that it is not based on damaged nerve cells, drew attention to the social causes of mental health in this sense. For example, the orientation of the gender problem between men and women, which traps women in secluded homes behind the society, is an important risk factor for the occurrence of psychological problems in women (Başterzi, 2017). The feeling of worthlessness, insecurity, and self-sufficiency experienced by women are among the factors affecting mental health. This debate about gender differences in mental illness has recently been reconsidered by national and international data. For example, the orientation of the gender problem between men and women, which traps women in secluded homes behind the society, is an important risk factor for the occurrence of psychological problems in women (Başterzi, 2017). The feeling of worthlessness, insecurity, and self-sufficiency experienced by women are among the factors affecting mental health. This debate about gender differences in mental illness has recently been reconsidered by national and international data.

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Since the early 1980s, studies on the relationship between race, ethnic status and mental health have begun to increase (Pilgrim and Rogers, 2005: 47). Studies pointing out stress as an important risk factor in the formation of schizophrenia and depression psychoses show that poor people are more prone to stress caused by negative life, housing, job and nutritional status, thus they are more likely to suffer from psychotic diseases (schizophrenia, depression, manic-depressive and suicide). discussed (Avison, McLeod, & Pescosolido, 2007). For example, in his book *Civilization and Madness* (2019), Scull revealed that while explaining the view of physicians in ancient Greece and China, attention was paid to the social aspects of this disorder:

“Even physicians who clung to organic explanations of mental disorder sometimes could not refrain from admitting that insanity was not a bodily condition and was decided by social condition. The social consequences of insanity often outweighed both families and imperial officials. Thus appeared a dull set of written legal doctrines, which were dull practical attempts to deal with the ravages of insanity, and in time to show officials the way to overcome insane acts and to direct families to rein in their insane relatives. For example, it can be said that interest in murders committed by insane increased towards the 17th century. These would look like “accidental murder due to lack of intent” (Scull, 2019: 46).

Since the 1960s, theories of labeling and stigmatization have been developed by Goffman (2018) on the socially negative consequences of an individual's diagnosis of mental illness. In this sense, although Goffman does not have the aim of setting up a theoretical basis for the sociology of mental health, it is an important pillar of the sociology of mental health. Goffman examined the admission, admission, obedience, and stigmatization processes of the insane in his work *The Asylums* (2016), and defined some collaborations with nurses and doctors, and some attitudes, reward and punishment systems, and formed the basis of defining a total institution.

“Another explanation must be given for the difficulties posed by sarcastic psychiatric approaches. As has been suggested earlier, the notion that “functional mental disorders” are in certain respects similar to the patterns of illness exhibited by someone with partial paralysis is partly based on the fact that in many cases it is extremely difficult to tell whether the patient is suffering from a functional or organic psychosis just by looking at the behavior. I think the assumption here is that the misbehavior of organically disabled patients is purely a symptom of illness, and if those with functional psychosis show these behaviors, it can be said that they also show some signs of illness. How a mental-origin disorder affects an entire behavioral pattern, just as it does in organic situations, is not explained.

Sociologists have critically examined the organization of mental health care, treatment use, and public policy. In addition, sociologists criticize the medicalization-medicalization theory by illuminating the social structure of mental illness by examining how deviant thoughts, feelings, and behaviors are transformed into symptoms to be treated medically. The sociological perspective emphasizes the impact of mental illness through social contexts, relationships, roles, and situations, apart from the biological mental health perspective, which shows genetic

and chemical imbalance in the brain as causes of mental illness. The sociology of mental health says that “madness” is not just a genetic issue but has a meaningful relationship with capitalism and neoliberalism. The dominant, biological "madness" discourse,

Approaches to Mental Health Sociology

Treatment of mental illnesses requires a long and intense labor process. In this treatment process, it is especially important to create a spatial area for the establishment of the necessary discipline and to meet the requirements of this area. The treatment applied during this long-term spatial isolation may lead to social problems such as stigmatization and exclusion from the society due to the spatial position of the patients (Goffman, 2016). Poverty, war and injustice are the main social, environmental and economic determinants of mental illness. Mental illnesses can occur due to biological, psychological, environmental and social causes.

Durkheim's conceptualization of social pathology can be mentioned in the context of the incompatibilities that arise with the conflict of the individual inner world and the outer world. Reality is not seen as something obvious, static, waiting to be discovered (Pilgrim & Rogers, 2005). In this context, the sociology of mental health can be defined as a problem that should be evaluated with a holistic perspective, considering the concept of mental health, which is considered only on the basis of physiological symptoms, together with other social factors. Mental health sociology examines the individual and the patient with the same importance as it examines the relationship between health and society in a broad context. The basis of mental health sociology is to explore the structural and social factors of the patient's illness. The basic assumption of the interactionist perspective is that reality is a product of social interaction and activity.

Structural Functionalist Approach to Mental Health

The structural functionalist mental health approach is a sociological approach that defines itself with an analogy between society and a biological organism. Just as the human body works in harmony with more than one organ and tissue that complement each other, society is produced with more than one system and social institutions living together in this sense. It is seen as a repairable machine when relations between social institutions are disordered. The structural functionalist mental health approach has the view that cutting out the unnecessary parts of the society will relieve the society. If individuals can successfully perform their roles, the social system will progress flawlessly. The implementation of the roles and responsibilities imposed on the individual in social life is especially important as the fulfillment of these role and role relations by the social person will ensure continuity in the society (Turner, 2017). The structural functionalist approach examines the concept of health in general within the framework of disease, social order, sick person and sick role. It emphasizes that health is a general organizational structure in the maintenance of social life. For a social balance, the definitions of health and disease are especially important according to functionalism. Supplying social harmony and order is possible by regulating these concepts of power. For a social balance, the definitions of health and disease are especially important according to functionalism. Supplying social harmony and order is possible by regulating these concepts of power. For a social balance, the definitions of health and disease are especially important according to

functionalism. Supplying social harmony and order is possible by regulating these concepts of power.

The incidence of mental illnesses in societies may differ with the extraordinary situations experienced in certain periods in societies. Societies may face situations such as war, revolution, social or economic crisis. At such times, the feeling of stress and uncertainty on the individual increases. In some societies, these uncertainties last for years, in some societies there is a certain political and social order. Therefore, the factors affecting mental health in the social context differ from society to society. The functionalist perspective basically explored the reasons behind these social facts rather than social facts.

Durkheim (2015) examined the relationship between social phenomena such as separation, going in and out of prison, being unemployed, economic crisis, and mental and nervous diseases. Durkheim (2015), who argues that social events negatively affect the balance in the individual psychological process, seeks the social effect on the basis of psychological disorder. Durkheim explains the conceptualization of anomie, which appeared due to the crisis of the social structure, with the rapid socio-economic developments experienced in the society. Durkheim (2015) also argued that an increase in mental problems is seen when a balance cannot be set up between the concept of anomie and the rapidly entering new era and the traditional life of the society.

Durkheim left his traditional life aside in modern urban life and said that the loneliness of the individual lost in the city lies at the root of mental distress. On the other hand, Durkheim, who says that over-integration negatively affects the spiritual life of the individual in traditional societies, emphasizes that society prevents individuals from behaving as they wish. Structural functionalism has little interest in the individual's experiences, goals, and feelings. It is thought that describing individual experiences is not important in constructing a macro social theory. Structural functionalists are more likely to ask, "What is the function of an individual's actions in forming a whole?" He thought about the question.

Symbolic Interactionist Approaches to Mental Health

Interactionism is an agent-centered theoretical paradigm that appeared after the 1960s. The concept of "perpetrator" is a concept that expresses the individual's ability to make his own decisions, what he can and cannot do. Symbolic interaction obviously includes an individual's mental flow and internal thought process, and social experiences with other people. However, the concept of "self" is one of the concepts used to understand the relationship of the social situation, the "me" in the group with the rest. Symbolic interactionism defines the role of the individual in everyday interactions as static, with change and process rather than continuity. Interactionism, built on the axis of the subject's thinking, experience and interpretation, roughly cares about the memories of the individual. Therefore, it is dynamic and open-ended.

Symbolic interactionism is basically "how does the subject interact with the society?", "what is the way for the individual to understand each other?" and "What are the reasons why individuals' everyday interactions are successful?" seeks answers to questions such as: Shared can also be defined as the process of sociality making meaning out of actions and symbols that may or may not have a specific meaning. The symbolic interactionist approach deals with many

subjects such as people's experience of social events such as birth, death, surgery, their reactions to illness and the analysis of doctor-patient interaction within the framework of mental health sociology. The conceptualizations of interactionism in mental health sociology suggest mental health, stigma theory, the origins and causes of behavioral deviations (Doğan & Kocacık, 2006). Sociology of mental health He argues that medicine stigmatizes patients especially on mental and nervous diseases. So, individuals who do not follow great social cultural norms in daily life are stigmatized as abnormal or deviant.

Howard Becker and Erving Goffman defined the concepts of “mental health”, “disability”, “stigma” and “insanity” from an interactionist perspective. Goffman, who decided a micro approach in which the individual is placed at the center, discussed the mental health spaces, examined the functioning of these spaces, their practices on patients, the effects of practices on patients, and the adaptation process of patients to these mental health spaces. Erving Goffman introduced the concept of "total institution", which explains mental health spaces, in his work called *Asylums* (2016) based on his observations in a mental hospital. Goffman's work called *Asylums* (2016) focuses on the world of asylum patients as actors and the analysis of their behavior. total institution, it is defined as the spaces that close the social situations of people whose boundaries are decided by the society with a certain temporal routine at a certain place in a certain period of time. Goffman defines the total institution as spaces that separate and discipline a large number of individuals with certain rules in a limited time period from the rest of their society. During the interviews, one of the interviewees said that the insane in his hometown (Tunceli) are considered sacred, and although he made a rational effort as a nurse in Bakırköy, he could not get away from that cultural coding (Health Officer, 2007-Working).

“What symbolizes the degrees of containment, or its total characteristics, are the barriers that he builds right next to the physical establishment, cutting off social contact with the outside: locked gates, high walls, barbed wire, cliffs and water, open space, and others. I call these total institutions and I want to investigate their characteristics” (Goffman, 2014: 204).

A total institution or space is a space isolated from the general public. One of the most distinctive features of these institutions is the spatial arrangement (such as barriers at the entrance and exit, high walls, iron bars, being in the forest, surrounded by water) (Goffman, 2016). The aim of the Total institution is “to destroy the identity of the closed” (Goffman, 2016: 65). In the context of the total institution, patients admitted to mental hospitals are deprived of their social roles and some of their freedoms. During the admission to the hospital, the anamnesis and personal biographies of the patients are learned, their examinations are conducted, and their belongings are confiscated. Thus, patients are forced to give up on themselves until they are discharged (Goffman, 2016). The purpose of depersonalization practices is to require the patient to actually set up a "me" suitable for the hospital (Goffman, 2016). Mental hospitals create tension between the patient's earlier life and hospital life. He uses this tension to make the doctor and nurse respect his power.

“Social institutions, in everyday terminology, are buildings or facilities within which regular activity is carried out [...] Each seizes something of the interests and time of its members and offers them a world; In short, every institution has encompassing tendencies” (Goffman, 2014: 204).

Disciplinary techniques running through various closure institutions also help to set up a control that individuals internalize over time. Thus, not only the desires, feelings and wishes of the individual; At the same time, the use of time and space begins to be guided by discipline techniques.

“The main reason these techniques are based on the arrangements of time and space while creating obedient bodies is to create the "economy of movements". For this reason, discipline techniques do not only condition the feelings, desires and actions of the individual; on the contrary, it should be able to organize time and space as the main factors that make them possible” (Özmkas, 2019: 60).

Another important work in terms of mental health sociology is Goffman's *Stigma* (2018). “Stigma” is the process of labeling the differences brought about by the outward appearance of individuals with disabilities or their action limitations (Goffman, 2018). The stigma is a product of social interactions and is especially important for perceiving the individual's experience of illness. The social stigma applied to the mentally ill is a sign of exclusion. A person who applies to psychiatry after a mental distress feels stigmatized, even if he or she is not faced with overt exclusion. In this context, the most basic source of the stigma process is the individual himself. As soon as the individual enters the process of being diagnosed with a disease or being admitted to a mental hospital, the feeling of stigma begins and self-esteem decreases (Goffman, 2016: 111).

Mental patients, analyzed by Becker (2015) within the sociology of deviance, offer an important perspective for the sociology of mental health. The definition of deviation is decided by different privileged groups in certain trials, according to Becker. However, this situation is rather than a process in which everyone describes a certain action as deviant in line with a command given from somewhere; In diverse cultures and different periods of political power, different mistakes are defined as heresy (Becker, 2015). In Becker's work, the fluid nature of deviation is discussed. In the sociology of mental health, interactionism keeps its place as an especially important and up-to-date view. Studies examining the mentally ill, the insane and mental health spaces have an important current value in sociology.

David Rosenhan (1973), who sees mental illness as a social phenomenon created by psychiatry's stigmatization of individuals, conducted an experiment to support this approach. Eight healthy subjects in the USA applied to twelve different mental health institutions and said that they had delusions and heard voices from the past. In fact, the subjects do not have such a delusion, but other than that, the subjects do not declare anything unrealistic, they describe their family history as it is. Seven subjects are hospitalized with a diagnosis of schizophrenia and one with a diagnosis of manic-depressive. While in the hospital, the subjects do not pretend, they act naturally, even it is said that they no longer hear sounds or words. Despite this, their normal behavior is recorded in the medical records as a symptom of schizophrenia or manic-depressive symptoms, and it takes two months for the subjects to be discharged. And it's not that they're improving on the record, symptoms are reported to decrease. When the hospital administrators said that such mistakes would never happen in their hospital after learning the results of the experiment, Rosenhan said that he would send fake patients to this hospital again in three months. At the end of this period, the hospital concluded that forty-one of the patients who applied to them were fake patients, while no fake patients were sent to the hospital. Rosenhan (1973) revealed that psychiatrists cannot distinguish between healthy and non-healthy ones. At the end of this period, the hospital concluded that

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Critical Theory-Based Approaches to Mental Health

Critical theory is defined as a structural analysis that assumes social inequalities and exploitation in relationships. According to this theory, the existing social structure will eventually lose its function and will open the door to a new egalitarian, free, just and peaceful golden age (Turner, 2017: 26). Critical theory, while dealing with mental health, evaluates a structural problem and draws attention to the economic-class dimensions of this structural problem. While going to this structural analysis, the dimension in which he deals with the situation is at a macro level (Turner, 2017). Although the health phenomenon, which he examines on the basis of institutions and cases, leaves the critical theory incomplete at some points, he makes especially important analyzes in general.

The critical approach examines the mental health issue as a structural problem in the light of macro data with concepts such as "mental illness", "health", "globalization", "capitalism", "justice", "marketing" and "exploitation". Critical theory, which discusses conflicts between individuals as power relations in the dimensions of doctor-patient, doctor-nurse, nurse-servant, has recently turned to micro-discussions. The critical theory, which argues that mental health and mental illness discourses develop within capitalist production relations, basically conducts its arguments in the name of an equal health service.

Marx's concept of "alienation" is especially important in terms of mental health sociology.

“Until the beginning of the twentieth century, the equivalent of the concept of “Alienation” in Turkish was not “alienation” but “madness”. The "alienist" derived from this concept is the "psychiatrist". Alienist was a common name given to doctors who were busy trying to help people who were alienated from society due to mental illness. Alienation was initially a concept that was only at the center of psychiatry and was used to express insanity, but over time it began to be used in various fields of social sciences and with different meanings. There is also an implicit reference to insanity in the use of the term alienation in the social sciences. In the alienation in philosophy and social sciences, there is a social and individual mental distortion, reasoning disorder. This phenomenon is madness in a way” (Artvinli and Erkoç, 2011).

Capitalist production relations that isolate and mechanize the individual are an important risk factor for the development of mental disorders. In this context, the alienation of the individual within the capitalist production relations can be defined as a risk factor for a mental disorder. Capitalist production relations that isolate and mechanize the individual, and social factors such as socially unequal capital and poverty, which are reflections of this, are among the factors that negatively affect mental health. In addition, mental disorders can negatively affect the social and economic life of the individual. In this sense, critical theory states that along with the negative effects of poverty on mental health, mental disorders can also lead to poverty. Critical theory has focused on the negative effects of poverty on mental

health. Individuals experiencing economic hardship may experience mental health problems such as physical illnesses, stress, introversion, loss of self-esteem, depression, anxiety and behavioral disorders. Social, economic and political variables can cause mental disorders.

Erich Fromm (2016), an important thinker in the sociology of critical mental health, questions the discourse of “normality” and says that every culture has a determined normal and while discussing the discourse of individual abnormality, he actually denies sociality (Fromm, 2016). Fromm is a social psychologist and psychoanalyst associated with the Frankfurt School. While developing his theory of the unconscious, Fromm (2005) defines reality as a phenomenon that occurs through the balance that is often in the middle ground between opposite extremes. Blending the ideas of both Freud and Marx, Fromm reconciles Freudian concepts such as the unconscious, biological drives, repression (the belief that character is decided by biology) with Marx's belief that humans are a product of themselves (Fromm, 2005). With this, Fromm's theory is not a mere blending of concepts; He adds the concept of "revolutionary freedom" to deterministic systems and tries to transcend the various reductions described by Freud and Marx.

While Freud was a major influence on Fromm, Fromm was part of a group that later became known as neo-Freudians, which included Karen Horney and Carl Jung. According to Fromm, who is known for developing the concept that freedom is a fundamental part of human nature and challenging the theories of Sigmund Freud, social disorders are destroyed in an environment where entertainment products (in Fromm's phrase, "drugs", for example, television) are given to hide social mental disorder. and injuries are all revealed (Ritzer, 2018). Fromm criticizes many of Freud's ideas, including the Oedipus complex, the life and death instincts, and the libido theory. Fromm believes that society and culture also play a key role in individual human development. He claims that although people enjoy having fun today, they are in a great mental depression, the individual has lost his sense of self and is dependent on the approval of the society (Fromm, 2005). While the word alienation is used to describe psychosis, which means completely disconnected from oneself, Fromm defines the alienated person as someone who is submissive to his own actions, disconnected from himself, and whose relationship with the outside world is not productive. Fromm argues that a sane society is one that constantly helps the individual to give birth to himself. According to Fromm, an unreasonable society is one that prevents the ongoing rebirth and puts the individual in a state of alienation (Fromm, 2005). While it is used to describe psychosis, which means completely cut off from himself, Fromm defines the alienated person as someone who is submissive to his own acts, cut off from himself, and not productively related to the outside world. Fromm argues that a sane society is one that constantly helps the individual to give birth to himself. According to Fromm, an unreasonable society is one that prevents the ongoing rebirth and puts the individual in a state of alienation (Fromm, 2005). While it is used to describe psychosis, which means completely cut off from himself, Fromm defines the alienated person as someone who is submissive to his own acts, cut off from himself, and not productively related to the outside world. Fromm argues that a sane society is one that constantly helps the individual to give birth to himself. According to Fromm, an unreasonable society is one that prevents the ongoing rebirth and puts the individual in a state of alienation (Fromm, 2005).

Fromm had a profound influence on humanistic psychology. He believes that life is a "contradiction" because people are both a part of nature and separate from it. For Fromm, out of this conflict appear basic existential needs, including relationship, creativity, rootedness, identity, and a framework of orientation. Conflicts of interest in the provision of basic

problematic health services, which critical theory focuses on in the field of mental health, and the source of illness and disability; It focuses on capitalist ideologies that support working class health, healthy living differences, doctor-patient communication.

Poststructuralist and Postmodern Approaches to Mental Health

Postmodernity is basically a critique of "modernity". At the same time, it includes an overly complex path on the basis of postmodern and post structural approaches, which we meet as a strict critique of structuralism, functionalism and critical thinking styles. There are similarities between feminist, critical theories and poststructuralist concepts in studies in the field of mental health sociology. The postmodern approach has created a break in the positivist monopoly of knowledge. With postmodern approaches, the objectivity of medical knowledge has been discussed and a medical control tool has been defined. As the critical theory emphasizes, the debates about the feeling of health as an economic profit tool have been among the other issues that have increased the interest in mental health sociology.

Poststructuralism has debated health, disease, the body, and the dominant medical discourse that defines normality. Poststructuralist thinkers argue that health discourse is used as a strategic discourse in managing and controlling individuals' right to have a say over their bodies. The poststructuralist approach makes two important contributions to the discussion of disease and health; It is a stance against the current medical discourse and the domination it creates, and conceptualizing medicine as a discourse that will discipline individuals. In the poststructuralist approach, the transformation of the body into knowledge and the medicalization of the body are defined as a process of social control. One of the tools of this social control function is mental health spaces.

The health discourse joins the debate that human experience and Western science are the only accepted legal and only way of thinking. The poststructuralist approach, which mostly shows medicine as the dominant discourse on health discourse, opposes this situation. One of the most important representatives of poststructuralism in this sense is Michel Foucault. Analyzing the social functions of the medical profession, clinical sciences and psychiatry, Foucault states that health is a social control tool and functions as a regulation. Foucault, with the discourse of insanity, expresses that he is trying to be shut down and "normalized" as a result of the fact that psychiatry sees them as individuals who were not seen as a disease in the past but should be closed. He said that clinical sciences do not actually create a certain certainty, they make themselves certain in order to have a say on the body, and he conceptualized that medicine is actually a positivity in this sense. On the other hand, Foucault (2015) defines the definition of positivity as a collection of information in an uncertain order and the manifestation of scientific information stacks-methods that are not fully precise in an orderly and formalized manner.

“Medicine as a social condition always creates disease [...] Medicine determines what is normal, appropriate, or desirable in every society, like laws and religion” (Illich, 2014: 38).

Foucault (2013), who argues that the body, which is a product of knowledge and power, has begun to be used as a control device in the modern age, states that the disease is not a natural pathological condition, on the contrary, it should be seen as a result of historical processes. Foucault states that those who have knowledge decide the discourse and have ideological power. Power continues to produce new forms of knowledge and discourse to

ensure social control (Foucault, 2013). In his book, *The Birth of the Clinic* (2012), Foucault defined that the social reality, which he called medical power, is decided from the beginning by health professionals. In the early 19th century, Foucault defined mental illnesses as a disorder of desire, passion and freedom (Foucault, 2009).

Institutionalized spaces in mental hospitals are heterotopias according to Foucault (Foucault, 1986). Foucault, who defines asylums as places of control, sees asylums as orthopedicization processes of people with the help of social sciences rather than seeing simple structures. According to Foucault, sociology turns into a tool of medicine (Foucault, 2019). What is wanted to be created with the panoptism used in the asylums is the surveillance society. As a result, medicine is part of a large and comprehensive system that lures individuals into their normal discourse.

Feminist Approaches to Mental Health

Feminist mental health sociology, which is organized by a male-dominated world and develops conceptualizations on the female body and psychology, benefits from both confrontational and interactionist approaches in terms of the subjects it deals with. The feminist approach, which is argued in many books to criticize the founding "fathers" of sociology, actually stands in opposition to this "fathers" discourse. Because he argues that sociology and all other sciences are written in male language, defined as "founding fathers" and this is wrong. The most important contribution of the feminist approach in terms of mental health sociology is that it defines gender inequalities in the field of mental health and shows the patriarchal point of view.

It is emphasized that women are exposed to more biological and psychosocial stressors than men, their job opportunities decrease, their education level decreases, they are physically abused by their spouses, they are victims of role conflicts in coping with social problems and they are more affected by poverty and illness experiences than men. (Ehrenreich, 1976).

One of the important risk factors affecting mental health is gender. Feminist mental health approaches argues that mental health should be examined differently for women, who are seen as the "second gender" who are under extreme pressure in some societies (Beauvoir, 2019). The feeling of marginalization and inadequacy caused by gender inequalities and experienced by women is one of the leading risks affecting mental health. In the National Trans Mental Health Report, which was published for the first time in 2013 in Australia, it was said that the stress and mental problems experienced by trans individuals are extremely high, especially anxiety and depression are common (Gürler, 2017).

Most discussions about mental health and gender tend to focus on women. Mental disorders can affect people differently. For example, some diseases such as depression and anxiety are more common in women and may have a more permanent effect on women than men (Ehrenreich, 1976). The disease state associated with mental illness has received much more attention than gender-specific determinants and mechanisms that promote and protect mental health and nurture resilience to stress and adversity. Gender decides the differential power and control of people over the mental health and socio-economic determinants of their lives, their social position, their status in society and their treatment, and their susceptibility and exposure to certain mental health risks.

Depression is significantly associated with interrelated and co-occurring risk factors such as anxiety, somatic symptoms, and high rates of comorbidity, gender roles, stressors, and adverse life experiences and events (Almeida & Kessler, 1998). The lifetime prevalence of alcohol dependence, another common disorder, is twice as high in men than in women (Almeida & Kessler, 1998). Gender-specific risk factors for common mental disorders that disproportionately affect women include gender-based violence, socio-economic disadvantage, low income and income inequality, low or secondary social status, and rank and unremitting responsibility for caring for others (LaPierre, 2009). An example of this is the high prevalence of sexual violence that women are exposed to and, so, the high incidence of Post Traumatic Stress Disorder following this type of violence (Thoits, 2009). The impact of long-term, cumulative psychosocial distress on mental health has not been adequately studied (LaPierre, 2009). Economic and social policies that cause sudden, devastating and drastic changes in income, employment and social capital that cannot be controlled or prevented significantly increase gender inequality and the rate of pervasive mental disorders.

Social Facts and Sociology of Mental Health

Sociologists working on the social meaning of health and mental illness have made various definitions on this subject. Simply, if we are sick, we are considered to be far from health, and if we are healthy, we are considered to be far from the disease. Mental health sociology basically discusses how and to what extent social regulations affect mental health by using official statistical information, symptom scales and diagnostic measurements obtained from psychiatry (Doğan & Kocacık, 2006). Efforts to set up a relationship between social roles and events on mental health is an especially important topic of discussion for the sociology of mental health. Variables such as gender, age, race, immigration, war can be given as examples of social roles and events.

War and Mental Health

War has many devastating effects, economically, culturally and politically, and as a result of war more deaths occur than any serious illness. In fact, although the number of deaths is looked at first in the balance sheet that appeared at the end of the war, negative consequences such as poverty, malnutrition, disability, economic/social decline, deterioration of the social structure and the development of mental illnesses occur apart from death. Scull also emphasizes the impact of war on mental health by saying that “an average of 5% to 30% of patients and wounded people evacuated from the battlefield are psychiatric casualties on all war fronts”. In this context, it is noteworthy that many hospitals and clinics were opened during the wars, such as the establishment of the first Islamic Bimarhane as a mobile war hospital during the Hendek War. The importance of post-war psychiatric disorders is underestimated in official statistics, but the incidence of psychiatric nervous breakdowns is highest at the height of the war. War damages all social structures, causes a lifelong mental disorder in families and a decline in financial capital. In the balance sheet that appears at the end of the war, the number of deaths is looked at first, but apart from death, the consequences such as poverty, malnutrition, disability, economic/social decline and mental illnesses are among the effects of wars (Murthy and Lakshminarayana, 2006). It causes a lifelong mental disorder in families and a decrease in financial capital. In the balance sheet that appears at the end of the war, the number of deaths is looked at first, but apart from death, the consequences such as poverty, malnutrition, disability, economic/social decline and mental illnesses are among the effects of wars (Murthy and Lakshminarayana, 2006). It causes a lifelong mental disorder in families and a decrease in

financial capital. In the balance sheet that appears at the end of the war, the number of deaths is looked at first, but apart from death, the consequences such as poverty, malnutrition, disability, economic/social decline and mental illnesses are among the effects of wars (Murthy and Lakshminarayana, 2006).

“Although 10% of people who experience traumatic events have severe mental health disorders, the other 10% show behaviors that cannot fulfill their physical functions.” (World Health Organization, 2001).

Problems such as the fear experienced by people whose families died during the war, the thought of being betrayed, the sexual harassment and rape that women and children are subjected to, and the uncertainty they feel in the camps they go to as refugees affect their mental health negatively. Refugees experience many mental symptoms and diseases such as insomnia, stress, anxiety disorder, prolonged grief reactions, major depression, anxiety disorders, somatization disorders (Yılmaz, 2014). It should be underlined that another problem faced by people who had to immigrate from their homelands due to the war is social exclusion and discrimination. Discourses involving stigmatization and marginalization against refugees settled in the cities are used to describe people who are forced to leave their country under difficult conditions and try to set up a new life in a country they do not know. It is one of the main factors that threaten the mental health of people who experience multiple victimizations” (Yılmaz, 2014). Many of those who are exposed to these discourses have difficulty in accessing mental health treatment services.

The World Health Organization has recently formed a special association for the development of “mental health and psychological support in emergency settings” (World Health Organization Regional Office for the Eastern Mediterranean, 2002). More than 20% of people living in conflict areas (and this number is three times higher than the rest of the world's population) suffer from mental disorders of severity ranging from mild anxiety to depression and post-traumatic stress disorder. In this context, the World Health Organization calls on states to make mental health and psychosocial support services an essential part of first aid in armed conflict and to integrate them into emergency response systems.

War is a collective experience, not a personal one, and the suffering it causes is socially resolved (Summerfield, 2001). The basis for understanding this collective experience is the social meaning ascribed to war, including supernatural, religious, and political causality. For this reason, members of a social group at war feel particularly helpless, seeing that what is happening to them is incomprehensible and that their traditional recipes for dealing with crises are useless (Summerfield, 2004). When war routinely targets the social fabric, society may not fulfill its usual roles as a source of support and cohesion. War causes social insecurity and further weakens communities as intended. The primary impact of the war on the victims was their history,

Children are among the most affected by the destruction. Children are not just passive bystanders, but active citizens with values and causes. The emergence of a wide variety of psychological symptoms and syndromes in conflict populations has been widely documented by current research. There is no doubt that in situations of war and conflict, society should receive mental health care as part of the overall relief, rehabilitation and reconstruction processes. As war gave a major impetus to evolving mental health concepts, as in the first half

of the 20th century, examining the psychological consequences of the current century's wars can bring new insights and solutions to general mental health problems.

The recent increase in trauma programs in war zones shows the danger of looking at war from a perspective borrowed from the psychiatry clinic and applying a paradigm that transforms the social into phytomedicine (Summerfield, 1987). Psychiatric models supply little insight into the role of social action and empowerment in promoting mental health. The greatest thrust of humanitarian interventions must be towards the war-weakened social fabric of the surviving population, for here lie the sources of resilience and the capacity to heal for all (Summerfield, 2004). Survivors first look to gain a measure of prestige and control over their environment and then re-establish the cultural, social and economic institutions and activities that are meaningful to them. These things, which define what it means to be human and civilized, are determined to preserve their culture and lifestyle as best they can (Summerfield, 2004). Basically, peacekeeping and peace-supporting is a mental health treatment method in itself, instead of drug treatment, against individuals who have been injured in war or exposed to the war environment.

Poverty and Mental Health

Poverty, a social problem that started from the very beginning of history and became more concrete with the industrial revolution; Increasing economic crises bring many processes such as unemployment, violence against women, divorce and suicide (Taşdemir, 2014). The lack of self-actualization opportunities of low-income and poor individuals creates a predisposition to deterioration of mental health. For this reason, it is accepted that there is a relationship between poverty and class position and mental health. While mood disorders are diagnosed equally in almost all social classes, there is a strong relationship between schizophrenia and social class (Doğan & Kocacık, 2006). The lack of self-actualization opportunities of low-income and poor individuals creates a predisposition to deterioration of mental health. It has been determined that the class characteristics of individuals who apply to mental health institutions for psychological support and counseling are an important factor in the diagnosis, and it has been stated that poor patients are more likely to be diagnosed with schizophrenia, and that biological treatment is applied rather than psychosocial treatment (Pilgrim & Rogers, 2005). The fact that the rate of the poor is higher among the patients hospitalized in mental hospitals is important in terms of understanding the relationship between poverty and mental health and deciding the risk factors that cause mental illnesses.

As risk factors, problems such as "adverse work conditions, poor living conditions, workload, uniformity of work, fear of unemployment, risk of accident, sexual harassment, sexual discrimination, racial discrimination, dual role stress in working parents" can be given as examples (Doğan and Kocacık, 2008). 2006). In fact, in a study conducted with 775 patients who applied to Bakırköy Mental Health and Neurological Diseases Training and Research Hospital Emergency Psychiatry Unit during August 2011, it was decided that 48% of the patients were primary school graduates and 77% were unemployed. Poverty affects mental health through a range of social and biological mechanisms that act on many levels, including individuals, families, local communities and nations. There is convincing evidence for a causal relationship between poverty and mental health. However, the findings

“Poverty is a situation that reduces human energy, hinders human life, and causes the individual to experience helplessness and loss of control of his life. If we consider the individual as a biopsychosocial disease, poverty has negative effects on mental health. II. The increase in mental disorders after World War II led to the emergence of the relationship between environment, socio-economic status and disease in post-war studies. The purpose of this article is to review the negative on poverty. Experiments with negative effects on the mental health of poverty experience” (Taşdemir, 2014).

In this sense, it is understood that poverty has many negative effects on mental health, especially negatively affecting the mental health of women, children and the elderly (Pilgrim & Rogers, 2005). In poor patients, psychosocial problems such as “socio-psychological incompatibility, lack of social skills, being aggressive or submissive, hopelessness, introversion, loss of self-esteem; Psychiatric diseases such as depression, somatoform disorders and schizophrenia are more common (Taşdemir, 2014). Considering the negative effects of poverty on mental health, the importance of creating healthy working and living conditions and providing active access to education, health and social security services emerges instead of short-term solutions such as partial aids in the prevention of poverty (Taşdemir, 2014).

Gender and Mental Health

Freud was the first to devise a systematic theory comparing the mental health of men and women. Classic Freudian theory holds that men are psychically superior to women. In general, Freud says that people buy a distinct sense of self during several stages of development (Galbis-Reig, 2003). According to Freud, in the phallic stage (around the age of 3-5), which is one of the stages of psychosexual development, sexual identity begins to develop, differences between the sexes are discovered, and the Oedipus complex, which marks the beginning of a radical separation between the sexes in the nature of the self (Gedo, 2002). In the Oedipus complex, the girl turns from her mother to her father as the primary love object, and thus the woman forms the Oedipus complex (Freud & Dantier, 2006).

Modern approaches question these general views and the basic assumptions of Freudian theory, as well as the most recent developmental theories (Sorell & Montgomery, 2001). All these theories postulate that people start out as fully connected to the world around them, especially their mothers, in such a way that they cannot distinguish between themselves and the outside world. Thus, these assumptions about how people develop suggest that men are favored and male psychology is superior. Stern instead suggests that humans begin as separate, disconnected creatures and become increasingly attached to those around them over time (Dietz, Kalof, & Stern, 2002). The self-relationship theory, named after Wellesley College, asserts that women's sense of self is strongly based on their connections with others (Palladino & Stephenson, 1996).

Recent large-scale epidemiological studies have evaluated rates of mental disorders in the United States (Kessler, 2003; Bedi, 2011; Spies, 2009; Baillie, 2005; Almeida and Kessler, 1998). These studies, which take all psychological disorders together, show that there is no difference in the mental health rates of people in general. Therefore, it is generally concluded that neither gender is more different than the other in terms of mental health. However, women surpass men in internalizing their anxiety and depression problems, in which problematic feelings turn inward (Tasca, Rapetti, Carta, & Fadda, 2012). This includes both milder and more

severe forms of depression, as well as most types of anxiety, including generalized anxiety disorder and phobias (Meyer, 2003).

There are two main reasons why women are more often diagnosed with psychiatric disorders, especially anxiety and depression: hospital records and social studies. These studies show that depression and anxiety disorders are higher in women, especially in married women, due to distress (Doğan and Kocacık, 2006). Basically, “single men are hospitalized more than married women, married women are more hospitalized for mental disorders than married men, and married men are more hospitalized for non-psychiatric diseases than married women” (Pilgrim and Rogers, 2005).

According to some researchers, if women do not conform to stereotypical gender roles such as motherhood and stay-at-home spouse, they are more likely to be labeled as mentally ill (Ehrenreich, 1976). There is male dominance in psychiatry and medicine, and feminist writers stress its importance. Depending on the culture, the “healthy woman” is considered more docile, less independent, more impressionable, less aggressive, less competitive, more self-loving in appearance, less objective. In terms of mental disorders, women are ahead of men in crime statistics. Men's behavior includes anti-social behavior, violence and sexual assault, and aggressive behavior with alcohol; women's behavior is more associated with self-harming behavior, depression, and eating disorders. Dangerous behavior towards others is more common in men. Self-destructive behavior is complex; Suicide attempt is more common in women and suicidal behavior in men. Low power feeling especially increases the risk of internalizing the symptoms (Arias, 2007).

“This economic injustice against women is perpetuated socially as well as individually. In the United Nations Development Program's “Human Development Report, Turkey ranks 109th out of 115 countries in terms of gender equality. In this report, it is said that the income of women in Turkey is 26% of that of men. It is emphasized that poor women are exposed to more biological and psychosocial stressors than men, their job opportunities decrease, their education level decreases, they are physically abused by their spouses, they are victims of role conflicts in coping with social problems, and they are more affected by the experiences of poverty and illness than men.

In response to differences in economic resources, men and women differ in their feelings of the amount of power they have in relationships. For example, individuals who think they have few alternatives to a relationship suffer higher levels of depressive symptoms than those who perceive they have more options. Gender differences in perceived strength also contribute to disparities in the internalization of symptoms between men and women. Looking at various levels, from broad socio-historical forces at the macro level to micro-level aspects of the self, we see how social differentiation by gender shapes the psychological problems of men and women. low power and responsibilities; factors such as low levels of self-esteem, autonomy, and self-disgust are consistent with mental disorders. In the mid-1970s, gender role theory became influential in discussions of why women are prone to internalized mental disorders (depression) and men to external disorders (substance abuse) (Cockerham, 2011). In many parts of the world, it is often said by social scientists that women are exposed to more discrimination than men, and that economic disadvantage also affects mental health.

Ethnicity and Mental Health

In the social sciences, race is typically used to describe "race relations" between oppressor and oppressed societies. In contrast, socio-cultural differences between groups are often referred to as "ethnicity." The term ethnicity defines a collective identity and the way of life of different ethnic groups is related to their own culture and their relations with other cultures (Avison, McLeod, & Pescosolido, 2007). While immigrants may become rich relative to their former status, they may be poor by the standards of the society in which they settled. Low wages, housing disadvantage and unemployment can make immigrants susceptible to the direct health effects of poverty. Migration itself and its consequences can be both physically and mentally traumatic.

Immigration of people of the same race and from the same place to the same place may cause them to racialize (not change in the new place) their way of life in the new country (Aneshensel and Phelan, 1999). The most common diagnoses of Irish immigrants to the UK are schizophrenia, neurotic disorders, personality disorders, depression, other psychoses and alcohol addiction. The reasons for such disorders and high hospitalization rates include poverty, hunger, suppression of some reaction rebellions by military force, forced migration (Avison, McLeod, & Pescosolido, 2007). This situation is intertwined with the identity crisis at the individual and social level.

“Here, perhaps paradoxically, the comparative approach does us some harm. Psychiatrists visiting foreign countries completely find the culture there strange and think that the language there is a difficult language to understand. However, the behavior of the mentally ill people from there is extremely familiar to them; for example, they once felt like they were in their own country while they were in the ward of the plighted patients who were locals. Psychiatrists often assume that mental patients are suffering from a culture-independent medical condition because they see themselves in a familiar setting when looking into a foreign examination room or examining the condition of an ostracized patient from there. However, here it is possible to consider the possibility that some of the etiquette specific to the situation may also be the basis for social communities in many diverse cultures. To the extent that there is such cross-cultural homogeneity, there are also internationally accepted non-conformities, and psychiatrists feel at home wherever they are in the world” (Goffman, 2020: 262).

Scull (2019: 182) defined the concepts of mental health and imperialism with the concept of "imperial psychiatry" and defined imperial western psychiatry applied against diverse cultures. Mental health centers have resulted in a massive closure that will spread to a certain extent to the rest of the world under the influence of Western imperialism over time. In British immigrant colonies (Canada, Australia, New Zealand) where Indigenous communities were partially destroyed or otherwise neutralized, mental hospitals modeled after British institutions appeared relatively quickly (Scull, 2019: 183).

“In the colonies, where there was only a small white ruling class, mental hospitals often entered the scene even later. The first mental hospitals in Nigeria were set up in the early 20th century and could not go beyond being places of detention” (Scull, 2019: 184).

With its political and cultural aspects, imperialism spreads the mentality of investing the insane all over the world; but it is only in some places that it succeeds in exporting the psychiatric major confinement, leaving aside the immigrant colonial states, which are remarkably similar to and follow in the footsteps of the homeland. Modern physicians had a contemptuous attitude

towards Indigenous beliefs and customs (Scull, 2019: 183). “No matter how much attempts were made to ignore, suppress and invalidate indigenous attitudes, these efforts were doomed to fail” (Scull, 2019: 185). Imperial psychiatry faced great difficulty in transforming local customs in such traditional societies.

“A lower-middle-class, middle-aged, male, Jewish, and immigrant psychiatrist can be seen making confident and detailed judgments about the symptoms showed by the emotional state of a lower-class, female, adolescent, and Black patient. This is an interesting achievement, as there are not many contacts where these two persons present can be present with the other or view the other's behavior as something natural and peaceful. Similarly, those who know a little about a mentally ill person and see him only during fleeting and short-term encounters are often inclined to easily see some of his or her actions as signs of mental illness. However, those who live with him do not care much about his movements and focus on some other behaviors.²⁵⁰ This is why, according to foreigners, Movements that are seen as signs of mental disorder, such as images of mentally ill people lying on the floor or taking food from their friend's plate, may be considered natural in the normative sense for those who are familiar with the environment in which the behavior is exhibited; because people who know that environment know that for example the sofas are not enough or are too hard, or sometimes there is enough food, just as a person can queue to get more food, they can also take food from their neighbor's plate. And again, we learn from psychiatrists themselves that the most backward and “primitive” types of movements are sometimes so “understandable” that the strange, meaningless quality of these movements is pushed into the background, and the human, poignant side comes to the fore instead” (Goffman, 2020: 256).

As can be understood from this quote from Goffman, some "abnormal behaviors" can be considered normal according to the members of the field. Basically, the lack of a full understanding of local beliefs and values paves the way for misunderstandings. The other is described as barbarian, as local customs and rituals do not fit with modern western traditions. If the definition of barbarian stays unaddressed, the definition of civilized has no place. Therefore, where the definition of insanity is perceived as the rituals of the local people, what is sick is actually a western perspective. Imperial psychiatry adds health to the political, economic and cultural phenomena transformed by imperialism. Societies that are forcibly brought under the culture of another administration in cultural, economic and political aspects believe that they are healthy and themselves unhealthy after a while. Because the western rational mind,

Imperial psychiatry has been often cited in the literature since the early 2000s. One of the most important names in this field is Frantz Fanon. His texts include *The Black Skin White Mask* (2015), *Essays on Alienation and Freedom* (2020) and *The Wretched of the Earth* (2018). *Towards the African Revolution* (1964) is published after Fanon's death. Many of Fanon's groundbreaking ideas appeared while he was working on mental illness as a psychiatrist in North Africa. Fanon was influenced by Marxism, psychoanalysis, and the philosophical perspective of Jean-Paul Sartre. Fanon accepted mental illness as a process that appears with experiences and presented a conceptual map at the point where mental illness is affected by society and culture. This conceptual map includes risk factors for mental illnesses,

The barriers to understanding the world in order to be unable to communicate also reveal the importance of language as a central feature of cultural revival and agency. Language not only structures the soul, but also the individual creates meanings through language. In this context, Fanon said that being understood and communicating through the native language is especially

important for mental health. This point can be examined under a subheading called “language and mental health”. It has been accepted by many theories (structuralism, poststructuralism, hermeneutics, symbolic interactionism, phenomenology) that language as a social phenomenon is a crucial factor in a social and individual formation process. In this context, language is an especially important field for mental health and mental health sociology.

Fanon directed his most severe criticism at crude colonial interpretations of psychosomatic diseases. The criticized psychiatric view is that colonized people are primitive and barbaric and therefore suffer from mental illness. Fanon does not see the body simply as a regressive field of psychological functioning. Instead, he argues that the body plays a crucial role in expressing and structuring the mind, helping to make us human. Fanon ultimately treats psychiatry as a form of discipline in the regulation of people. It sees this as a proxy control mechanism for those who do not manage the double-binding nature of oppressive colonial contexts.

Social Integration and Mental Health

Emile Durkheim's *Suicide* (2015) is often considered the first sociological study to openly discuss mental health. Durkheim compares suicide rates at the end of the 19th century with populations and various social characteristics in different European countries. In this study, Durkheim basically shapes the relationship of the individual's interactions with social institutions and suicide. Saying that people with strong social interactions are least likely to commit suicide, Durkheim states that socially isolated people are more likely to commit suicide. For example, Durkheim says that married people have lower suicide rates than unmarried people. Also, Durkheim (2015: 222),

Current research in the sociology of mental health emphasizes the importance of social integration as the root cause of mental health. For example, people who have closer contact with family, friends and neighbors and who take part in voluntary organizations such as churches, non-governmental organizations and clubs report better mental health than those who are more isolated (Thoits, 2009). Married people experience less distress than unmarried people because they have more supportive relationships and more ties to community institutions (LaPierre, 2009; Umberson, Williams, Powers, Liu, & Needham, 2005). Marriage also serves regulatory functions that promote compliance with social norms, more traditional lifestyles, and lower levels of deviation of any kind. On the contrary, the death of relatives, the loss of social ties and the breaking of romantic ties that divorce can cause are associated with increased levels of distress. Social integration is associated with positive mental health, people get satisfaction. When the individual is deprived of valuable, intimate relationships, he suffers.

Social Stratification and Mental Health

The mental and spiritual response to social inequalities is also based on fundamental dimensions of social life. Social processes affect what problems people have, what remedies they look for, and what resources they find to treat problems and how they categorize them. Elements that define class status, such as economic capital, inequalities in power, knowledge, influence, and prestige, have powerful effects on mental health (Link & Phelan, 1995). In addition to such social inequalities, poor working conditions, uninsured work, marital problems and unhealthy living conditions are also associated with mental health (Link & Phelan, 1995). Impoverished social conditions have a significant impact on mental health. On the other hand, an important

debate within the sociology of mental health is the question of whether the effect of social status and economic well-being on mental health is absolute or relative. Does social welfare depend on the absolute or relative amount of resources people have? If absolute wealth predicts happiness, then the rich will have good mental health and the poor will have worse mental health. For example, the fact that a very wealthy businessperson has less success or less income than those in his status may put him in a bad position among those in his status. As can be understood from this situation, social, cultural and economic capital is not the only condition that has a significant impact on an individual's mental health. Does social welfare depend on the absolute or relative amount of resources people have? If absolute wealth predicts happiness, then the rich will have good mental health and the poor will have worse mental health. For example, the fact that a very wealthy businessperson has less success or less income than those in his status may put him in a bad position among those in his status. As can be understood from this situation, social, cultural and economic capital is not the only condition that has a significant impact on an individual's mental health. Does social welfare depend on the absolute or relative amount of resources people have? If absolute wealth predicts happiness, then the rich will have good mental health and the poor will have worse mental health. For example, the fact that a very wealthy businessperson has less success or less income than those in his status may put him in a bad position among those in his status. As can be understood from this situation, social, cultural and economic capital is not the only condition that has a significant impact on an individual's mental health. For example, the fact that a very wealthy businessperson has less success or less income than those in his status may put him in a bad position among those in his status. As can be understood from this situation, social, cultural and economic capital is not the only condition that has a significant impact on an individual's mental health. For example, the fact that a very wealthy businessperson has less success or less income than those in his status may put him in a bad position among those in his status. As can be understood from this situation, social, cultural and economic capital is not the only condition that has a significant impact on an individual's mental health.

However, the most important reason for the depression of millions of people working under precarious, poor working conditions and low wages is income inequality created by social stratification. Problems arising from income inequality affect housing, nutrition, education and many social processes. Individuals who cannot go to a good school, cannot supply healthy nutrition conditions, and cannot stay at home in good conditions need the elimination of social inequalities rather than larger mental health centers. Social stratification is not only related to economic and working conditions, but also related to all social institutions. For example, the dominant party in a marriage reports better mental health than the less powerful partner (Link & Phelan, 1995). Since husbands are generally stronger than wives, generally have better mental health. However, this is not always the case. In the relatively few cases where married men have fewer resources than their wives, they experience more distress than their wives (Rosenfield, 1992).

Conclusion

Mental health sociology is a discipline that aims to understand the mental and mental health of individuals by relating them to the social, political and economic dynamics of society. This approach emphasizes that mental health depends not only on individual factors, but also on societal and structural factors. Mental health sociology explores the impact of social interactions, societal norms, institutions, and power relations on individuals' mental health. Factors such as the social and cultural structure of the society, social classes, gender,

ethnicity, age, sexuality can create risks and protective factors for mental health. This discipline also examines inequalities in access to mental health services. Differences in access to economic resources, health insurance, community support networks and health services It can lead to injustices among individuals with mental health problems. Mental health sociology does research that strives to achieve social justice by emphasizing these inequalities. In addition, the sociology of mental health examines the feelings and attitudes of society about mental health. The presence of stigma towards the mental health of the community may affect the help-seeking behavior of individuals, their application to mental health services, and adherence to treatment. Therefore, mental health sociology, which considers social norms, media and cultural factors, works on reducing stigmatization and creating a more supportive environment for the mental health of the society. In conclusion, mental health sociology emphasizes that mental health is a complex social phenomenon. In addition to individual factors, social, it tries to understand that political and economic contexts also have important effects on mental health. This discipline aims to supply equal access to mental health services of the community, to reduce stigma and to support the mental health of the community.

works to get closer.

Source

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[1] Mental Health Spaces in the Context of Space and Sociology of Mental Health This is the second part of the master's thesis named Bakırköy Mental Health and Neurological Diseases Training and Research Hospital Example.